

Macrocyclic nickel(II) complexes of some polynucleating aza ligands

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Abstract : The template syntheses of nickel(II) complexes of three polynucleating aza macrocycles 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,21-octaazaspiro[10.10]heneicosane (OASH), 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DOCD) and 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaaza-1,6,17,22-tetrachlorotricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DTTD) have been reported. The formulation of the new products as $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OASH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DOCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DTTD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ have been supported by elemental analyses, conductivity measurements and spectroscopic studies. The potentiometric study on the nickel(II) complexes of DOCD indicating the existence of $[\text{NiH}_x(\text{DOCD})]^{(x+2)+}$, $[\text{Ni}_2\text{H}_y(\text{DOCD})]^{(y+4)+}$ and $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DOCD})]^{6+}$ species in solution ($x = 8, 7, 6, 5, 4$ or 3 ; $y = 4, 3$ or 2) is also in agreement with the proposed structure.

Keywords : Nickel(II), macrocyclic, complex.

Introduction

A considerable number of macro-polynucleating compounds particularly the bi- and tricyclic ring systems have been synthesized. Most of the reported polynucleating macrocycles include the ligands capable of incorporating more than one metal-ion within a large ring¹⁻⁴ and the macrocycles consisting of many cyclic sub-units connected by a single bridge or more bridges⁵. More than one linkage between the cyclic sub-units will tend to reduce the flexibility of the system, usually enable the relative positions of the metal centres to be controlled more precisely, for example, 'co-facial' dimers⁶. In search of a further category of such macro-polycyclic ligands, recently we have reported⁷ the condensation of some tetraaza macrocyclic ligand complexes of copper(II) derived from triethylenetetramine, and chlorocarbon (carbon tetrachloride, 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane and hexachloroethane) with 1,2-diaminoethane in presence of copper(II) ion to yield large macrocycles consisting of three rings, 1,4,7,10,12,15,17,20,23,26,27,30-dodecaazadispero[10.4.10.4] triacontane (DDST), 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DOCD) and 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaaza-1,6,17,22-tetrachlorotricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DTTD). The present work is the extension of similar reactions to the nickel(II) ion. The nickel complexes of

DOCD and DTTD have been synthesized but the corresponding product of DDST could not be crystallized from the condensed reaction mixture. In addition, nickel(II) complex of a new macrocycle 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,21-octaazaspiro[10.10]heneicosane (OASH) has also been derived from the condensation reaction between carbon tetrachloride and triethylenetetramine present in 1 : 2, molar ratio (Fig. 1). The potentiometric equilibrium studies on the DOCD hydrochloride and its nickel complexes are in structural support.

Experimental

Chemicals and reagents :

Solvents and reagents used were of reagent grade and were used without further purification. The solutions of CO_2 -free 0.1770 N NaOH, 0.02159 N HNO_3 and 1.0 M KNO_3 were prepared for potentiometric equilibrium studies. DOCD.12HCl was synthesized as reported earlier⁷, and its aqueous solution (0.005 M) was prepared by direct weighing.

Physical and chemical measurements :

Elemental analyses were performed by the Central Drug Research Institute, Lucknow. Ionizable chloride ions in the sample were determined by conductometric titrations¹. The metal complexes were decomposed and the metal content was estimated by complexometric titration

Fig. 1. Reaction scheme.

method⁸. A DDR conductivity meter (Type 304) was employed for conductivity measurements. Infrared spectra (FTIR) in the range 4000–350 cm^{-1} were recorded on a Shimadzu 820 IPC spectrophotometer using KBr disks. ^1H NMR spectra were run on a Bruker DRX 300 (300 MHz FT) in D_2O solution using DSS as an internal standard.

Potentiometric titrations :

The following mixtures : (i) 0.002159 *N* HNO_3 ; (ii) 0.0005 *M* $\text{DOCD} \cdot 12\text{HCl}$ + (i); (iii) 0.0005 *M* nickel nitrate + (ii); (iv) 0.001 *M* nickel nitrate + (ii) and (v) 0.0015 *M* nickel nitrate + (ii) prepared in 50 mL and were titrated pH-metrically at 25 °C and at ionic strength of 0.1 *M* KNO_3 using an EC 5656 pH-meter with combined electrode system. From the experimental data titration curves (pH vs moles of alkali used per mole of ligand, *a*) were plotted and analyzed^{9,10} for obtaining information on the existing metal-ligand equilibria.

Synthesis of the nickel(II) complex of 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,21-octaazaspiro[10.10]heneicosane (OASH) :

Nickel hydroxide (5.00 g, 53.92 mmol), triethylene-

tetramine (7.89 g, 53.95 mmol) and carbon tetrachloride (4.15 g, 26.98 mmol) in 200 mL butanol were stirred and refluxed for 2 h, 30 min. Before heating a mixture of light green precipitate and green solution was obtained. After 10 min of heating it changed to a mixture of green precipitate and light brown solution. The green precipitate changed to light brown, its amount decreased and the light brown solution turned into a brown solution in the mixture after 30 min. Finally, after continuous heating for 1 h, it turned into a mixture of brown precipitate and dark brown solution. The cooled mixture was stirred with 80 mL of water and filtered. The dirty green residue was rejected and the reddish-brown aqueous layer of the filtrate was separated from the non-aqueous wine red layer. Brown platelets of the product $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OASH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was obtained when the aqueous solution was concentrated and refrigerated. The product was washed with ether and dried. Yield was 2.40 g.

Synthesis of the nickel(II) complex of 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0⁶.17]dodecacontane (DOCD) :

The nickel(II) complex of the macrocycle 11,12-

dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane prepared as described in literature¹¹ was employed as one of the reactant for the synthesis of nickel(II) complex of 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane. A mixture containing (11,12-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane)diaquanickel(II) chloride (8.78 g, 21.58 mmol), nickel hydroxide (1.00 g, 10.78 mmol) and ethylenediamine (1.30 g, 21.63 mmol) in 100 mL butanol was stirred for 5 min and heated to reflux. A continuous heating of the greenish-violet turbid mixture for 14 h yielded a dark violet turbid solution. The resulting solution was filtered after stirring with 50 mL water, and the aqueous brown layer of the filtrate was separated from the non-aqueous light red layer. The green residue was rejected. Concentration and evaporation (under reduced pressure) of the aqueous solution left a brown sticky solid. After removing the sticky matter by benzene/ether treatment as described earlier¹, the brown solid was dissolved in 50 mL methanol. Addition of equal amount of acetone caused precipitation of a brownish-violet powder. The analytical pure brownish-violet product $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DOCD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 24\text{H}_2\text{O}$ was filtered washed with 1 : 1, methanol-acetone mixture and dried. The yield was 2.12 g.

Synthesis of the nickel(II) complex of 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaaza-1,6,17,22-tetrachlorotricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DTTD) :

Two step condensation reaction was carried out to yield nickel(II) complex of 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaaza-1,6,17,22-tetrachlorotricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane. At first step a mixture of nickel hydroxide (4.00 g, 43.13 mmol), triethylenetetramine (6.31 g, 43.15 mmol) and hexachloroethane (10.21 g, 43.13 mmol) was refluxed in 120 mL butanol for 2 h, 30 min. Generation of the macrocyclic ring 11,11,12,12-tetrachloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacyclododecane was expected⁷ from a colour change, light green to brown but its complex with nickel(II) could not be isolated. At the second step a stirred mixture of nickel hydroxide (2.00 g, 21.57 mmol) and ethylenediamine (2.59 g, 43.09 mmol) in 60 mL butanol was added to the first refluxed but cooled mixture. The content was again stirred for 5 min and then refluxed for 6 h. The resulting mixture left a brown precipitate after 3 h and finally, a brown turbid solution was obtained after 6 h. The mixture was cooled and stirred with 80 mL of water. The aqueous brownish-red layer was separated from the residue and the wine-red non-aqueous layer as described in other systems. It was concentrated and then allowed to stand at room temperature for 7 days to yield

a brownish-pink semi-solid mass. Brownish-pink crystals of the product $[\text{Ni}_3(\text{DTTD})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]\text{Cl}_6 \cdot 18\text{H}_2\text{O}$ were obtained on the filter paper after treatment of the semi-solid with benzene/ether and dried. The yield was 2.86 g.

The condensed product (Ni-DDST complex) of equimolar 1,2-diaminoethane and (11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane)nickel(II) chloride ($[\text{Ni}(\text{DTCU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$) from the refluxed reaction mixture could not be crystallized. An equimolar mixture of carbon tetrachloride, triethylenetetramine and nickel hydroxide (nickel hydroxide 5.00 g) in 150 mL butanol was refluxed for 2 h to yield $[\text{Ni}(\text{DTCU})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]\text{Cl}_2$ as described earlier.¹² A 2 : 1 mixture of 1,2-diaminoethane and nickel hydroxide (2.5 g) was then added and the resulting mixture was refluxed for 5 h during which time its colour changed from yellowish-brown to brown. After stirring the mixture with 100 mL of water the grey residue (negligible amount), non-aqueous red layer (oily) and the brown aqueous layer were separated as usual. Finally, concentration and refrigeration of the aqueous solution did not yield the macrocyclic product.

Results and discussion

Synthesis :

Recently, we have reported that the triethylenetetramine condenses with carbon tetrachloride in presence of nickel hydroxide in the equimolar mixture of the reactants. An eleven membered ring product 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU) containing two unreacted Cl atoms is generated¹². But, in the template reaction involving nickel hydroxide, triethylenetetramine and carbon tetrachloride in 2 : 2 : 1 molar ratio, described here a dinuclear nickel complex of the macrocycles 1,4,7,10,12,15,18,21-octaazaspiro[10.10]heneicosane (OASH) is formed. Two molecules of $\text{Ni}(\text{NH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH} \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_2 \cdot \text{NH}_2)(\text{OH})_2$ condense with one molecule of carbon tetrachloride. The generated bicyclic ligand accommodates two nickel ions in its cavities. Each nickel is coordinated to four aza groups (Fig. 1).

The condensation of the tetraaza ligand complexes of nickel derived from equimolar amounts of triethylenetetramine, chlorocarbons containing four or more Cl atoms (carbon tetrachloride, 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane or hexachloroethane) with 1,2-diaminoethane in presence of the corresponding metal hydroxide is expected to yield the metal complex of a large macrocycle. Thus, the nickel(II) complexes of two large macrocycles each containing three fused rings 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-

dodecaazatricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DOCD) (derived from 1,1,2,2-tetrachloroethane) and 2,5,7,10,13,16,18,21,23,26,29,32-dodecaaza-1,6,17,22-tetrachlorotricyclo[20.10.0.0^{6,17}]dotriacontane (DTTD) (derived from hexachloroethane) have been isolated from 2 : 2 : 1 molar mixture of the mononuclear tetraaza metal complex, 1,2-diaminoethane and corresponding metal hydroxide. Each complex is a trinuclear complex and each metal ion coordinated to four aza donors is accommodated in separate cavity (Fig. 1).

The elemental analyses and conductivity measurements support the formulation of the new macrocyclic compounds (Table 1). The structures of the macrocycles have been confirmed by the infrared and proton magnetic resonance spectra. The IR bands are strongly suggestive of the cy-

660, 556 and 540 cm⁻¹ attributed to O-H stretching, bending, rocking bands are due to skeleton vibrations of the whole complex molecule.

DOCD system :

The bands assigned to stretching and bending modes of water in the trinuclear nickel complex with DOCD are seen at 3263 (strong) and 1641 cm⁻¹ (medium, very sharp), respectively. The rocking, wagging and $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ bands of coordinated water appear at 764, 664 and 592 cm⁻¹, respectively. The weak bands at 2932, 2882 (very sharp) and 1462 cm⁻¹ (sharp), respectively, are assigned to C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and $\delta(\text{C-H})$ modes. A very weak but very sharp band at 1146 cm⁻¹ is attributed $\nu(\text{C-N})$. A very sharp band at 525 cm⁻¹ assigned to $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$.

Table 1. Analytical and physical data of the macrocyclic complexes

Compd.	Colour (Colour at D.P.)	Yield (%) (m.p. °C)	Λ_M ($\Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2$ mol ⁻¹)	% Found (Calcd.)					Molecular weight Found (Calcd.)
				C	H	N	Ni	Cl ^a	
[Ni ₂ (OASH)(H ₂ O) ₄]Cl ₄ .15H ₂ O	Brown	9.87	500	17.30	7.82	12.40	13.01	15.76	-
Ni ₂ C ₁₃ H ₇₀ N ₈ O ₁₉ Cl ₄	(...)	(189)		(17.31)	(7.84)	(12.42)	(13.02)	(15.72)	(902.1)
[Ni ₃ (DOCD)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₆ .24H ₂ O	Brownish-violet	14.18	668	17.36	7.88	12.08	12.74	15.30	-
Ni ₃ C ₂₀ H ₁₀₈ N ₁₂ O ₃₀ Cl ₆	(black) ^a	(160)		(17.33)	(7.87)	(12.13)	(12.71)	(15.34)	(1386.2)
[Ni ₃ (DTTD)(H ₂ O) ₆]Cl ₆ .18H ₂ O	Brownish-violet	9.37	730	17.01	6.55	11.90	12.41	15.07	-
Ni ₃ C ₂₀ H ₉₂ N ₁₂ O ₂₄ Cl ₁₀	(violet) ^b	(200) ^d		(16.96)	(6.56)	(11.87)	(12.44)	(15.02)	(1415.9)

^aBlack at 255 °C; ^bblack at 252 °C; ^cionizable chloride ion; ^ddecomposition point.

lic nature of the macrocycles, there being an absence of the bands due to coordinated or free -NH₂ groups^{1,2,13,14}.

Infrared spectra :

OASH system :

The nickel complex of the macrocyclic ligand exhibits a very weak but very sharp band at 3150 cm⁻¹ frequency assigned to the N-H stretching modes. The corresponding $\delta(\text{N-H})$ vibration (very weak, very sharp) is seen at 1595 cm⁻¹. The C-H vibration frequencies of the complexes (2925, 2870 and 1460 cm⁻¹ for asymmetric) are comparable with the corresponding frequencies in the nickel-DTCU complex probably due to structural similarity and identical ring size. The weak but very sharp bands of $\nu(\text{C-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibrations appear at 1070 and 470 cm⁻¹, respectively. The presence of coordinated water is indicated by the appearance of medium bands at 3370 and 1640 cm⁻¹ followed by other peaks at 760,

DTTD system :

Nickel-DTTD complex spectrum exhibits a very weak but sharp band at 3161 cm⁻¹ attributed to N-H stretching vibration of secondary amine. The presence of these two bands and absence of bands due to free or coordinated NH₂ suggest that the complex is a macrocyclic molecule. Coordination of the macrocyclic ligand through nitrogen is indicated by a very weak but sharp band at 469 cm⁻¹ assigned to metal-nitrogen stretching frequency. Coordination of water is supported by the presence of strong and broad band at 3271 cm⁻¹ ($\nu(\text{O-H})$ mode), followed by bands at 1639, 760, 667 and 523 cm⁻¹ attributed to $\delta(\text{O-H})$, rocking, wagging and twisting modes of H₂O molecules, respectively. A very weak but sharp band due to $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ vibration is seen at 469 cm⁻¹. Very sharp bands at 2936 (medium), 2883 (medium) and 1462 cm⁻¹ (strong) are assigned to C-H asymmetric, symmetric stretching and scissoring modes, respectively. The $\nu(\text{C-N})$

N) appears at 1113 cm^{-1} as a very weak but sharp band.

Comparison of IR data with related systems :

The nickel or copper ions are coordinated to four aza groups of 11,11-dichloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (DTCU), 11-chloro-1,4,7,10-tetraazacycloundecane (CTCU) or OASH in their cavities consisting of bridge combination 2,2,2,1. In the nickel complexes the $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration frequency follows the order : OASH > CTCU > DTCU. The lowest value in case of DTCU complex is expected due to presence of two Cl-atoms which reduce the Ni-N electron density. This effect is comparatively poor in the CTCU complex. But, in the OASH complex the Ni-N bond order is highest in absence of any inductive effects. The $\nu(\text{N-H})$ vibration frequency in these complexes follows a reverse trend (i.e. DTCU ~ CTCU > OASH). The $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ vibration at 540 cm^{-1} in each system shows that coordinating tendency of H_2O molecules to the complexes is identical. Further, there is no regular order in the C-N stretching vibration (CTCU ~ OASH > DTCU). The bond order Cu-N > Ni-N is shown by the stretching metal-nitrogen vibration frequencies in copper and nickel complexes of DTCU. In addition, the $\nu(\text{N-H})$ or $\nu(\text{C-N})$ vibration frequencies as expected follow the order : Ni > Cu.

In the copper(II) complex of DDST the two side rings have bridge combinations similar to that in OASH (2,2,2,1) or other macrocycles described above where each metal is coordinated to four aza groups. The size of the middle ring, because of its bridge combination 2,1,2,1 is a slightly reduced. Probably due to this reduction in size of the middle ring the Cu-N bond order in DDST complex is not much greater than Ni-N bond order in nickel-OASH complex. Further, the greater Cu-N bond order in DDST complex than in DTCU complex, as indicated by the $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ vibration frequencies in their copper complexes is due to absence of an inductive effect in DDST complex.

The ring cavities in DOCD and DTTD macrocycles are identical in size where each ring ($[\text{12-N}_4]$) has 2,2,2,2 bridge combination. Metal-free macrocycles are planar molecules. The $\nu(\text{Ni-N})$ vibration frequencies at 469 and 525 cm^{-1} , respectively in nickel complexes of DTTD and DOCD show lower Ni-N bond order in DTTD complex than in DOCD complex. The reduction in Ni-N bond order in DTTD complex is probably due to inductive

effect of four Cl atoms bonded to the macrocycle. The $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ vibration frequencies in both the complex are identical.

The $\nu(\text{Cu-N})$ vibration in copper complexes of DTTD or DOCD shows that the copper complex is stronger than the corresponding nickel complex. Also, as expected the Cu-N bond order in DTTD complex is lower than that in DOCD complex because of electron-withdrawing effect by four Cl atoms in DTTD.

Unlike DOCD or DTTD which are planar, the macrocycle 2,5,8,11,13,16,19,22,23,26,29,32-dodecaazatricyclo[10.10.10.0]dotriacontane (DTCD)¹² is three-dimensional molecule. But, its smaller ring structures containing bridge combination 2,2,2,2 are similar to those of DOCD or DTTD. The Ni-N bond order in nickel-DTCD complex is lower than that in the corresponding DOCD complex, probably due to non-planar structure of DTCD complex and the steric hindrance caused by the three compact rings. The $\nu(\text{Ni-O})$ bond order DOCD > DTCD is also probably due to over-crowding of coordinated water molecules in nickel-DTTD complex. The low Ni-N bond density in nickel-DTTD complex as compared to that in the corresponding DTCD complex is further expected in view of inductive effect by Cl atoms in DTTD complex.

¹H NMR spectra :

A sharp peak in the ¹H NMR spectrum of DOCD hydrochloride at 4.72 ppm is expected for NH_2^+ protons. Another signal of a complex multiplet with many peaks centered at 3.54 ppm is expected for CH_2 protons. Further, the ¹H NMR spectra of the DOCD complex with nickel(II) is consistent with the spectrum of the ligand which show NH signal at 4.68, and very complex multiplet, expected for remaining protons, centered at 3.50 ppm. In the ¹H NMR spectra of the nickel(II) complexes with DTCU and DTCD, the signal for NH proton resonances have been reported at 4.78 and 4.68 ppm, respectively. Further, for the DTCU complex, a hump was observed in 4.10-2.25 ppm region which assigned to CH_2 proton resonance. But, in the DTCD complex a broad doublet expected for methylene proton appeared in 4.00-1.80 ppm region.

Solubility, conductivity and other data :

All the macrocyclic products are highly soluble in water and moderately soluble in many polar solvents like

methanol, ethanol, DMF, DMSO, etc. Their molecular conductivity and the number of ionizable chloride ions are recorded in Table 1. $[\text{Ni}_2(\text{OASH})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_4]\text{Cl}_4 \cdot 15\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 4 : 1 electrolyte exhibiting molar conductance $500 \Omega^{-1} \text{cm}^2 \text{mol}^{-1}$. The molar conductance values for the remaining complexes are consistent with a 6 : 1 electrolyte. The nickel complexes of OASH, DOCD and DTTD are brown, brownish-violet and brownish-pink, respectively. The 15, 24 and 18 lattice water molecules in the nickel complexes of OASH, DOCD and DTTD, respectively, lost on heating up to 120 °C indicates that these water molecules in the complexes are not coordinated to metal ion. The nickel complexes of OASH and DOCD melt at 189 and 160 °C, respectively. The nickel complex decomposed to a black solid at 255 °C. But, the corresponding complex of DTTD decomposed to violet solid at 200 °C and then to black solid at 252 °C.

Solution stability :

Dissociation of nine out of twelve protons from DOCD.12HCl below pH 11.0 has been reported recently. The titration curves of 1 : 1, 1 : 2 and 1 : 3 nickel : DOCD.12HCl systems show three inflections at $a = 4, 8$ and 12, respectively, indicating formation of $\text{NiH}_8\text{A}^{10+}$, $\text{Ni}_2\text{H}_4\text{A}^{8+}$ and Ni_3A^{6+} in steps as in Cu-DOCD system (Fig. 2). Only five and two protons of $\text{NiH}_8\text{A}^{10+}$ and $\text{Ni}_2\text{H}_4\text{A}^{8+}$ dissociate between $a = 4$ and 9, and 8 and 10, respectively, up to pH 11.0. The corresponding equilibrium constants are given in Table 2.

In 1 : 1, nickel : DOCD.12HCl system the four NH_2^+

Table 2. Equilibrium constant of nickel(II) complexes of DOCD at 25 °C ($\mu = 0.1 \text{ M KNO}_3$)

Reaction	log K''
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{H}_8\text{A}^{8+} \xrightleftharpoons{K''} \text{NiH}_8\text{A}^{10+}$	5.71
$\text{NiH}_8\text{A}^{10+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_1'} \text{NiH}_7\text{A}^{9+} + \text{H}^+$	-7.24
$\text{NiH}_7\text{A}^{9+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_2'} \text{NiH}_6\text{A}^{8+} + \text{H}^+$	-7.95
$\text{NiH}_6\text{A}^{8+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_3'} \text{NiH}_5\text{A}^{7+} + \text{H}^+$	-8.74
$\text{NiH}_5\text{A}^{7+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_4'} \text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+} + \text{H}^+$	-9.62
$\text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_5'} \text{NiH}_3\text{A}^{5+} + \text{H}^+$	-10.44
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{NiH}_4\text{A}^{6+} \xrightleftharpoons{K''} \text{Ni}_2\text{H}_4\text{A}^{8+}$	8.43
$\text{Ni}_2\text{H}_4\text{A}^{8+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_1''} \text{Ni}_2\text{H}_3\text{A}^{7+} + \text{H}^+$	-8.70
$\text{Ni}_2\text{H}_3\text{A}^{7+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_2''} \text{Ni}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+} + \text{H}^+$	-10.02
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{Ni}_2\text{H}_2\text{A}^{6+} \xrightleftharpoons{K'''} \text{Ni}_3\text{A}^{6+} + 2\text{H}^+$	-12.86
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{A} \xrightleftharpoons{K_1} \text{NiA}^{2+}$	11.67 ^b
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{NiA}^{2+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_2} \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+}$	10.17 ^b
$\text{Ni}^{2+} + \text{Ni}_2\text{A}^{4+} \xrightleftharpoons{K_3} \text{Ni}_3\text{A}^{6+}$	11.14 ^b

^aValues are $\pm 0.04-0.14$; ^bapproximate value.

Fig. 2. pH vs α curves : (1) DOCD.12HCl, (2) Ni^{2+} -DOCD.12HCl, (3) 2Ni^{2+} -DOCD.12HCl and (4) 3Ni^{2+} -DOCD.12HCl (DOCD.12HCl = 0.0005 M).

groups of only one ring of the ligand with lowest pH values are expected to be involved in coordination like that in the copper system. Also from a comparison of pK_5^H , pK_6^H , pK_7^H and pK_8^H of the ligand hydrochloride with the pK_1' , pK_2' , pK_3' and pK_4' of the NiH_8A^{10+} , respectively, a large deviation in value ($pK_5^H - pK_1' = 1.56$, $pK_6^H - pK_2' = 1.65$, $pK_7^H - pK_3' = 1.41$ and $pK_8^H - pK_4' = 0.93$) is indicated. Hence, uncoordinated NH_2^+ groups of the complex NiH_8A^{10+} with pK_1' , pK_2' , pK_3' and pK_4' are expected to be associated to the second ring adjacent to metal coordinated ring. Also, from a comparatively low $pK_9^H - pK_5'$ value (0.41) and liberation of no proton from $Ni_2H_2A^{6+}$ indicates that the related protons are away from the metal coordinated ring. Thus, in 1 : 1, metal-ligand system the single metal ion is accommodated in one of the two side rings. The second ion in 1 : 2, metal-ligand system enters the middle ring.

The equilibrium constant values for K' , K'' and K''' are given in Table 2. But, the exact values of the equilibrium constants for the reactions involving the formation of non-protonated species NiA^{2+} , Ni_2A^{4+} and Ni_3A^{6+} (K_1 , K_2 and K_3 , respectively) could not be evaluated from the experimental data as many protons of the third ring of the metal-free ligand or nickel coordinated NiH_3A^{5+} and $Ni_2H_2A^{6+}$ species do not dissociate under the experimental condition. But, the expression $K_1 = K' \cdot K_1' \cdot K_2' \dots K_8' / K_5^H \cdot K_6^H \dots K_{12}^H$ can be simplified for obtaining an approximate value of K_1 . As discussed above, the pK values of the NH_2^+ groups related to the third ring of the metal-free macromolecule and its nickel complex NiH_8A^{10+} are expected very close to each other (i.e. $pK_{10}^H \sim pK_6'$, $pK_{11}^H \sim pK_7'$ and $pK_{12}^H \sim pK_8'$). Thus, $K_1 = K' \cdot K_1' \cdot K_2' \dots K_5' / K_5^H \cdot K_6^H \dots K_9^H$ was used to evaluate approximate K_1 value. Similarly, the approximate K_2 and K_3 values can be obtained from the approximate relations $K_2 = K'' \cdot K_1'' / K_5'$ and $K_3 = K''' / K_3'' \cdot K_4''$ as described in copper-DOCD systems. The macrocyclic

effect in coordination by the ligand is reflected from high value of equilibrium constants, K'' , K_1 , K_2 or K_3 . Comparatively low K''' value is due to protonation of the ligand.

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